

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan - Final

Q-PLAN

31/03/2026

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Executive Summary

This document constitutes the final version of the INSPIRE project's Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP), due in M18 of the project. It has been developed by Q-PLAN, in collaboration with ERDN and input from all partners, under Work Package 6 “Communication, dissemination and exploitation” and Task 6.1 “Dissemination and communication”.

INSPIRE aims to support the sustainable and inclusive development of European rural areas by promoting social well-being and inclusion of rural dwellers and groups in a vulnerable situation and enhancing governance frameworks in rural areas. In particular, the project contributes to advancing in a multi-dimensional way the concept of social inclusion in rural areas, and supports access to high-quality social services by rural citizens through a series of awareness-raising, capacity-building, and pilot deployment activities that focus on social entrepreneurship and improvement of social services in a set of 7 different pilot territories (e.g., coastal, rural, peri-urban, mountainous). To realise its objectives, the project provides a novel territorial typology of rural areas, sets up and operationalises 7 “Smart Village labs”, and enhances governance frameworks and informed policymaking through E-Democracy and user-innovation techniques, to eventually deliver a dedicated Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard.

With reference to the initial report elaborated in D6.1, the document at hand describes the overall communication and awareness-raising activities, dissemination of project results, management of all relevant activities, and partners' involvement in this respect. It includes specific actions and activities that have been and will be carried out by the INSPIRE consortium members to ensure success and maximum publicity for the project and its results. With that being said, this deliverable outlines:

1. **What to disseminate** – Chapter two is devoted to the basic project-related information that has been and will be conveyed throughout the project;
2. **To whom** – Chapter three consists of the key stakeholder groups that serve as the main audiences for the project's dissemination and communication activities;
3. **How** – Chapter four includes all the channels and tools that are being utilised by project partners in order to successfully implement the dissemination and communication activities;
4. **When** – Chapter five provides a time frame to ensure that the timing of the dissemination and communication activities is appropriate, during the lifespan of the project and beyond;
5. **Monitoring of the process** – Chapter six identifies and calculates the indicators to measure success in the dissemination and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts and actions over the course of the project.

By M3, the first DCP framework had been established. From that point until M18, the project implemented actions based on this plan while continuously refining them to achieve stronger results. A strong and recognisable visual identity was established with a logo, templates, and promotional materials that supported consistent messaging. The project website and social media accounts were launched and have been maintained with regular updates. An animated video was produced and widely promoted (reaching 1,819 views), while two newsletters and four press releases were issued. Scientifically, the project has delivered four conference presentations. Participation in external events has also played a key role, with partners participating in twelve external events, such as conferences

to present project developments and results at both national and international levels. In addition, collaboration with related initiatives has also been a vital component of D&C, with seven synergies established so far.

A final deliverable “D6.4 – Dissemination and communication results” will be available at the end of the project (M36). It will include the results and metrics of the dissemination and communication activities.

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Table of Terms and Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NoI	Network of Interest
PAs	Practice Abstracts
SMA	Social Media Accounts
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled “D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan - Final”, presents the updated strategy, planning and implementation framework for dissemination and communication actions under the INSPIRE project. Building upon the initial version D6.1, this updated deliverable reflects the project’s evolving context, progress, and lessons learned from the initial implementation phase. Keeping that in mind, this deliverable outlines the approach to (i) effectively convey the project’s objectives, results, and impact, (ii) guide the partners in designing, planning and implementing their individual dissemination activities, and (iii) continuously monitor the efficiency and the timeliness of these actions. In this respect, the deliverable aims to:

- Describe the types of dissemination channels and tools that have been and will be utilised, along with the required actions and resources;
- Define responsibilities among partners;
- Summarise the internal monitoring, evaluating, and reporting of dissemination activities;
- Provide an indicative timetable/work planning of promotion activities during the project.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

Taking the above into consideration, the “Dissemination and Communication Plan - Final” is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1 – Introduction:** Provides introductory information (scope, objectives, structure) with respect to the DCP
- **Chapter 2 – Dissemination assets:** Presents the main assets and information of the project during and beyond its span
- **Chapter 3 – Targeted stakeholder groups:** Presents the main audiences for the project’s dissemination and communication activities
- **Chapter 4 – Channels and tools:** Encompasses all the channels and tools utilised for the project’s dissemination and communication activities.
- **Chapter 5 – Time plan:** Provides the timeframe for the communication and dissemination activities of the project partners
- **Chapter 6 – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and monitoring:** Defines the indicators to measure success in the dissemination and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project
- **Chapter 7 – Conclusions:** Pertains to the main decisions and aspects of the DCP as well as the way forward

The Annexes include the dedicated forms for the dissemination and communication activities (guidelines, project templates, news reporting form, external events and “Dissemination and Communication reporting template”) to facilitate collaboration within WP6 and ensure useful resources for the project channels.

The methodology of INSPIRE for dissemination and communication builds on know-how, tools and templates that were developed internally by Q-PLAN as well as on good practices and templates from the literature. As in previous EU-funded projects, tailored modifications to the methodology were implemented for INSPIRE as well, in order to comply with the GA conditions and the particularities of the project. Along these lines, this deliverable presents the adjusted methodology as it was further developed and applied in the context of INSPIRE, as well as presents the results from its application during the project.

2. Dissemination assets

The assets that follow have been and will continue to be disseminated by all partners with a view to maximising the project’s impact and visibility. This information will be conveyed in a meaningful way and well-tailored to each stakeholder group (these groups will be further described in Chapter 3).

- **Vision, objectives, strategic relevance, and key facts:** The vision, aim and strategic objectives of the project are widely disseminated along with all the conceptual aspects of the project, namely the whole project concept and its innovative characteristics.
- **News, achievements, and results:** During the project, news, achievements, and results are published through press releases and news items, on the project’s website or partners’ websites to inform stakeholders about the project and its contribution to social inclusion in rural areas.
- **Events held by the project or in which partners will participate to present their results:** The events organised by the project, as well as those in which partners participated to present their results, are being widely disseminated to attract targeted stakeholder groups.
- **Key project results:** Key project assets, as depicted in the following Table 1, are disseminated as widely as possible in order to stimulate the interest of prospective end-users and lay the ground for their post-project rollout.

Table 1. INSPIRE’s main assets/results¹

INSPIRE’s main assets/results
KER1: Social inclusion framework in rural areas
KER2: Repository of (social) services, initiatives and policies
KER3: Smart Village lab in Kosice Region (Slovakia)
KER4: Smart Village lab in Lubelskie Province (Poland)
KER5: Smart Village lab in Kythera Island (Greece)
KER6: Smart Village lab in Konitsa Municipality (Greece)
KER7: Smart Village lab in Bourgogne Franche-Comté (France)
KER8: Smart Village lab in Eastern and Midland Region (Ireland)
KER9: Smart Village lab in Suceava and Maramures (Romania)
KER10: Social economy solutions deployment roadmaps
KER11: MOOCs of European capacity building programme
KER12: Network of Interest
KER13: Policy briefs
KER14: INSPIRE Guidebook and Toolkit
KER15: Territorial typology of EU rural areas

¹ Exploitation and sustainability. These are the INSPIRE’s exploitable results which have been evaluated and identified as KERs by partners at this stage (D6.5, 31/03/2025).

INSPIRE's main assets/results

KER16: Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment

KER17: Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard

KER18: INSPIRE monitoring and evaluation framework

KER19: Quantitative & Qualitative datasets

3. Targeted stakeholder groups

The key stakeholder groups targeted via the dissemination and communication activities of INSPIRE are outlined in the following table:

Table 2 INSPIRE’s main target groups

Groups	
Groups in a vulnerable situation ²	Including migrants, minorities, elderly people, women (in vulnerable situations), people with physical disabilities, people with intellectual disabilities, employees in the informal sector, mountain farmers
Public sector	Including regional authorities, local authorities, public social service providers
Academia	Including universities, researchers, research centres
Private sector	Including social enterprises, local SMEs, capital investors, private service providers, universal designers, cooperatives
EU-wide stakeholders	Including EU policymakers, relevant DGs, EU-funded projects
Civil society	Including urban commuters, local NGOs
Other	General public, citizens, open platforms for sharing data and lessons learnt, etc.

² The identification of vulnerable groups is inherently context dependent. Consequently, groups considered vulnerable may vary across pilot sites and may differ from those identified in other rural areas across Europe.

4. Channels and Tools

INSPIRE uses a blend of online and offline communication channels and activities with a view to maximising the project’s visibility to its stakeholders. These channels and activities are presented in the list as follows:

- ✓ Graphical identity (logo, branded templates for reports and presentations)
- ✓ Promotional material (leaflet, poster, banner), videos, and newsletters
- ✓ Project website
- ✓ Project social media accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, Bluesky, X and YouTube and partners’ social media accounts
- ✓ Participation in external events and conferences
- ✓ INSPIRE’s events (workshops and Final Conference)
- ✓ Synergies with relevant projects/initiatives
- ✓ Network of Interest activities
- ✓ Practice Abstracts

The dissemination and communication assets of the project will continue to be distributed through the above-mentioned channels and tools to all targeted groups. This process involves all the activities depicted in Figure 1. Q-PLAN has provided dedicated guidelines for the expected use of communication and dissemination channels to the consortium. These are listed in Annex I.

Figure 1: Dissemination and communication activities

The following table lists key channels for dissemination that will continuously be used throughout the course of the project. It also includes dissemination channels that are being used in the pilot areas to reach out to their ecosystems.

Table 3. INSPIRE's dissemination main channels

Channel	Description	Groups
Publications in scientific journals	The researchers of INSPIRE disseminate the research results via scientific articles and conference presentations	Academics and scientific community, policymakers and public authorities, relevant initiatives and networks
International/national conferences	The researchers of INSPIRE disseminate the research results via conference presentations	Policymakers, the academic and scientific community, relevant initiatives and networks, private sector actors
Workshops and networking events	Several events embedded in the design of INSPIRE (e.g., pilot warm-up events, EU-wide networking event, capacity building workshops, co-creation workshops, MOOCs programme) address targeted groups of stakeholders, disseminating our results while also facilitating their exploitation.	Groups in a vulnerable situation, business actors, policymakers, the academic community, relevant initiatives and networks, civil society, other
Communication activities	INSPIRE's communication activities (website, social media, synergies with other projects, events, etc.) communicate and disseminate key project results	Policymakers, academia, relevant initiatives, industry, and civil society, other
Social media	Sharing pilot activities on local Facebook and other social media channels	Locals in the pilot areas
Messaging applications (Viber group)	Creation of local Viber groups to share information, coordinate with participants, and maintain continuous communication among members of the Lab and interested citizens.	Locals in the pilot areas
Email communication	Distribution of invitations and information about workshops and awareness-raising activities through targeted email lists of local stakeholders and participants	Locals in the pilot areas
Printed material	Printed invitations and posters placed in public spaces to inform residents about upcoming events and encourage participation.	Locals in the pilot areas
Local press	Local news outlets such as community Newsletters, newspapers	Locals in the pilot areas

In addition, the following table summarises a preliminary set of the key messages addressed towards each targeted stakeholder group of INSPIRE, as well as the set of dissemination and communication tools of the project used to convey them.

Table 4. Key messages and tools used for INSPIRE's targeted stakeholder groups

Target group	Tools and channels	Key messages
Groups in a vulnerable situation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, MOOCs, Smart Village labs, Dissemination package Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE increases social well-being by offering inclusive social services based on social economy.
Public sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, Nol, Guidebook, Smart Village labs, Atlas, Policy briefs, Dashboard 	INSPIRE upgrades governance framework for

Target group	Tools and channels	Key messages
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	social inclusion and social economy in rural areas.
Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, Nol, Guidebook, Atlas, Dashboard Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE provides knowledge and new datasets on social exclusion, social services and social economy and rural growth.
Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, networking events, Nol, Guidebook, Atlas, Dashboard Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE enhances knowledge of social economy solutions and user innovation practices for rural development.
EU-wide stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, Nol, Guidebook, Atlas, Dashboard Publications in scientific journals, International/national conferences, Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE delivers policy solutions for social economy and social services in rural areas.
Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, MOOCs, Networking events, Guidebook, Smart Village labs Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	INSPIRE provides access to opportunities and augments social inclusion through enhanced social services.
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website, SMAs, workshops, MOOCs, Networking events, Guidebook, Smart Village labs Workshops and networking events, Communication activities 	

4.1 Graphical identity and promotional material

The INSPIRE visual identity was created through a well-planned branding strategy that includes the logo, colour palette, slogan, and fonts. The goal is to help make the project easily recognisable and memorable to its audience. All communication activities, such as newsletters and press releases, consistently adhere to the project's branding guidelines. This uniformity strengthens recognition, builds familiarity, and ultimately fosters trust and loyalty among stakeholders.

To ensure a consistent visual style across all outputs, branded templates for reports and presentations have been developed. These templates support alignment in both internal and external communications. In addition, a range of promotional materials, such as leaflets, posters, and banners, has been created to effectively convey the project's key messages, attract attention, and stimulate engagement. These promotional materials are primarily used at project events, workshops and external events attended by INSPIRE partners, while also contributing to the project's ongoing visibility and everyday promotion.

Each partner is responsible for translating (if needed) and printing these materials based on their local requirements. Pilot partners specifically have a dedicated budget to print dissemination material to be distributed in their communities, so translations of the materials are considered essential in their cases, to be able to appeal to a wider audience. Partners should always consult and request approval

from the Dissemination Manager/T6.1 Leader, Q-PLAN, before producing any kind of promotional material.

4.1.1 Project logo

The INSPIRE project logo was developed on the eve of the project (M2) to meet the visual and graphic requirements of the project. During the INSPIRE 1st monthly meeting, various logo options were presented to the project partners in order to allow them to express their preferences and select their favourite design. The chosen logo of INSPIRE was adopted in agreement with the absolute majority of partners and is presented in Figure 2 - Figure 5.

Figure 2: INSPIRE's project logo, version 1

Figure 3: INSPIRE's project logo, version 1 - tagline

Figure 4: INSPIRE's project logo, version 2

Figure 5: INSPIRE's project logo, version 2 - tagline

The project's logo is a combination mark, which means that it is composed of a combined wordmark and a distinctive pictorial/icon mark. The icon and text are integrated together to create an image.

The logo design for this project is primarily centred around a font-based approach, emphasising the project's acronym. Given the inherently memorable nature of the project's name, the strategic use of robust typography serves to enhance brand recognition significantly. The deliberate choice of a modern font aligns with the project's essence, effectively conveying its contemporary and forward-thinking attributes. This design approach underscores the project's commitment to creating a visually impactful and memorable brand identity.

The icon of the logo, as presented in Figure 6, encapsulates a circular shape, which consists of curved lines and 7 small circles symbolising the 7 Smart Village labs. The shapes created remind the viewer of people coming together in a circle, depicting inclusive communities that are connected. The earthy colours are a reference to nature and rural areas (including peri-urban, coastal and mountainous areas), but they also refer to the inhabitants, inclusion and innovation.

Figure 6: INSPIRE logomark

The symbiotic integration of these elements in the icon contributes to a distinctive and meaningful visual representation of the project's mission.

The logo colours are used in all possible circumstances to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of INSPIRE. The chosen colour palette seamlessly integrates various shades of green, red, brown and purple. The main colours are two shades of green (#617570 & #829C94), two shades of red (#BF5C4D & #DE7A69), two shades of brown (#66402E & #A67857) and one shade of purple (#736675) linking inhabitants of rural areas (including peri-urban, coastal and mountainous areas) with inclusion and innovation. The colour palette used for the project is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: The colour palette of INSPIRE

In any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc., produced within the scope of the INSPIRE project, the EU flag and funding acknowledgement, as depicted in Figure 8, must be prominently displayed.

Figure 8: The EU flag and funding acknowledgement

In compliance with the EU requirements on dissemination of results, as set in Grant Agreement number 101136592, Article 17, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must display the EU emblem with appropriate prominence and also include the following disclaimer:

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4.1.2 Project leaflet, poster, and infographic

The project [leaflet](#), [poster](#) and [roll-up](#) constitute an important pillar of communication activities and present essential project information (aim, objectives, partners, etc.). They were created in January 2025 (M4).

In a nutshell

INSPIRE promotes wellbeing and inclusion for people living in European rural areas, through research, policy solutions and pilot interventions. It analyses social inclusion and access to social services in rural areas and provides capacity-building on social entrepreneurship to rural citizens, with an extra focus on vulnerable groups. Smart Village Labs in seven pilot areas empower the local community and promote social entrepreneurship.

Project objectives

- To provide an understanding of what social inclusion is and its trends and challenges in rural areas through research that includes hard-to-reach populations.
- To map and benchmark (social) service policies, initiatives, and social economy models to assess their potential and limitations, informing policies through a "Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment".
- To enhance existing governance frameworks for social inclusion and social economy in rural areas, through Smart Village Labs.
- To co-develop, pilot and evaluate social economy solutions for social inclusion and better service access in rural areas.
- To provide policymakers with research tools and policy recommendations in a Guidebook on social inclusion, service access of vulnerable groups and rural social economy.

PROJECT PARTNERS

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	University of Barcelona web.uib.edu	Spain
	South East European Research Centre www.seerc.org	Greece
	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague www.czu.cz	Czechia
	KOÇ University www.ku.edu.tr/en	Türkiye
	Social Economy Europe ASBL www.socioeconomy.eu.org	Belgium
	The European Association of Service providers for Persons with Disabilities easpd.eu	Belgium
	European Social Network www.esn-eu.org	Belgium
	European Network of Migrant Women www.migrantwomenetwork.org	Belgium
	PEDAL Consulting s.r.o. www.pedal-consulting.eu	Slovakia
	European Rural Development Network erdn.eu	Poland
	MedINA - Mediterranean Institute for Nature and Anthropos med-ina.org	Greece
	L'ADAPT www.ladapt.net	France
	The Wheel www.wheel.ie	Ireland
	ROMONTANA www.romontana.org	Romania
	Q-PLAN International Advisors PC www.qplan-intlgr	Greece
	ARX NET AE web.arxnet	Greece

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Supporting the inclusion, well-being, and growth of rural areas through multi-actor Smart Village labs* for enhanced governance frameworks

* Smart Village labs are physical and virtual places that promote social inclusion through user innovation and social entrepreneurship, based on a participatory approach and the use of digital technologies.

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Stakeholders

OR WHO COULD BENEFIT FROM THE PROJECT

The key stakeholders for sharing the project's results are categorised as follows:

- Groups in a vulnerable situation, including migrants, minorities, elderly people, women, people with disabilities, employees in the informal sector
- Public sector, regional and local authorities and public services
- Academia
- Private sector, social enterprises, local SMEs, private service providers and designers
- EU-wide stakeholders, EU policymakers and EU-funded projects
- Civil society

PROJECT IDENTITY

Project Title: Supporting the inclusion, well-being, and growth of rural areas through multi-actor Smart Village labs for enhanced governance frameworks

Grant Agreement No: 101136592

Start: 1 October 2024

Duration: 36 months

Budget: c 4,999,991.25

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Project Methodology

INSPIRE envisions to support the sustainable development of rural areas in Europe through a three core interrelated phases methodology:

- 1. MAPPING PHASE**
Researching (i) social inclusion and marginalisation in European rural areas on a micro, meso and macro level and (ii) social economy and delivery of services in European rural areas.
- 2. PILOT INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES PHASE**
Developing the Smart Village labs to support bottom-up community engagement, governance frameworks and social entrepreneurship, and to offer capacity building to rural citizens and mentoring to breakthrough social economy ideas.
- 3. SUSTAINABILITY PHASE**
Initiating a discussion with policy public authorities on inclusive rural governance through a policy Network of Interest and equipping policy makers with tools: a Replication guidebook and a Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard.

INSPIRE Pilot Cases

INSPIRE sets up Smart Village labs in seven pilot areas to:

- Support social inclusion and participatory governance through E-Democracy tools, boosting participatory democracy, connecting all key stakeholders and empowering rural dwellers and vulnerable groups towards decision-making.
- Offer EU-wide and localised capacity building for upskilling and empowerment of rural populations, supporting entrepreneurial initiatives developed in the framework of the project and assisting the labs' transition into "Smart Villages" and the participatory and digital upgrade of the pilot areas governance frameworks.

- 1. KOSICE REGION, SLOVAKIA**
PTVG: disabled persons, young disabled people, elderly people, and Roma people
- 2. LUBELSKIE PROVINCE, POLAND**
PTVG: people working in agriculture, women and Ukrainian refugees
- 3. KYTHERA ISLAND, GREECE**
PTVG: unemployed youth
- 4. KONITSA MUNICIPALITY, GREECE**
PTVG: ethnic minorities-refugees, unemployed youths elderly people
- 5. BOURGOGNE FRANCHE-COMTÉ, FRANCE**
PTVG: people with disabilities
- 6. EASTERN & MIDLANDS REGION, IRELAND**
PTVG: elderly, young unemployed persons, and migrants
- 7. SUCEAVA AND MARAMURES, ROMANIA**
PTVG: elders, youths and ethnic minorities of Ukrainians, Ruthenians, and Hutsuls

*PTVG: Potentially targeted vulnerable groups
 Traditional rural territory Island/coastal territory
 Mountainous territory Peri-urban territory

Figure 9: INSPIRE's leaflet/flyer

Figure 11: Indicative photos from the warm-up events and co-creation workshops

Beyond these core materials designed to engage a broad range of stakeholders from researchers to the general public, further promotional content has been (e.g., a [project overview presentation](#)) and will be developed as needed throughout the project to support specific INSPIRE events or announcements.

For instance, a factsheet has been prepared by SEERC on measuring social inclusion and wellbeing in rural Europe to communicate key results of Deliverable 1.1 (available in [infographics](#)), or a new interactive game "Build Your Smart Village" was built by MedINA for approaching the local communities in the Greek pilots, along with key chains and tote bags with the project logo. This adaptive approach ensures responsiveness to the specific requirements articulated by individual partners, thereby enhancing the efficacy of communication initiatives associated with the project.

Figure 12: Board game and tote bags of the Greek pilots

4.1.3 Templates

Branded templates have been developed to support consortium partners in preparing their deliverables and presentations (available since M2, earlier than originally designed, which was for M4). These templates ensure a consistent, professional appearance across all project materials, reinforcing brand identity and enhancing recognition among audiences.

The INSPIRE presentation templates incorporate key elements of the project's visual identity, including the logo, brand colours, fonts, and brand elements from the project's visual identity. Dedicated templates have been created for both project deliverables and partners' presentations and are readily available to all consortium members. In addition, an INSPIRE letterhead has been

Figure 13: Factsheet on measuring social inclusion and wellbeing in rural Europe (page 1)

designed to support various communication activities, such as event invitations and official correspondence, further contributing to the project’s cohesive visual presence.

The following templates have been prepared for the INSPIRE project:

- INSPIRE presentation template;
- Project deliverables and reports template;
- Project letterhead.

The templates are provided in Annex II.

INSPIRE will continue to develop promotional materials and templates if needed. By building on existing core materials, the project can maintain a cohesive identity while adapting content to specific audiences and event needs. This approach strengthens credibility, maximises outreach, and helps retain and refine effective messaging for future activities.

4.1.4 Promotional video

An animated informational video, as depicted in Figure 14, was chosen to enhance the project as through visual storytelling, the animation captured attention and simplified key information, helping audiences understand and retain the project’s core concepts. The project informational video, approximately two (2) minutes in length, was produced in M12 to effectively reinforce the project’s communication activities. The preparation of the video was the responsibility of Q-PLAN. The video provided an overview of the project, including vital information, and served as an engaging way to highlight the mission and vision of the project. It has been uploaded to the [INSPIRE YouTube channel](#) as well as on all the project’s social media. Up until M18, the video has collectively received **1,819 views**.

Table 5: Informational video views³

Social media	Views
Youtube	531
LinkedIn	895
Facebook	356
Bluesky	(info not available)
X	37
Total	1,819

³ Updated on 27/03/2026.

Figure 14: INSPIRE's Informational video

4.2 INSPIRE's digital presence

4.2.1 INSPIRE's website

The project website is a key communication tool, enhancing both the visibility and the overall impact of the INSPIRE project. It serves as a central platform to present the project's progress and milestones to a wider audience.

Launched in M6 (March 2025), the [INSPIRE website](#) functions as the primary online hub for public outreach. It has been carefully designed for ease of navigation and clarity, providing comprehensive information on the project's concept, objectives, and ongoing developments. It also features regular updates on news and upcoming events. Figure 15 shows the website's homepage.

Figure 15: Website

Q-PLAN is the partner responsible for the website's design, development, maintenance, and overall management. Special care has been taken to ensure the site is fully responsive and accessible across a wide range of devices, including mobile phones and tablets.

A dedicated report titled “**D6.3 INSPIRE Website**” was elaborated in M6 by Q-PLAN, focusing on the website's structure and content. The deliverable can be found [here](#).

As the main gateway to all INSPIRE-related activities, the website hosts a wide array of resources, including:

- A detailed overview of the project's concept and objectives.
- Information on the project consortium and the Smart Village Labs (which will be further elaborated as the labs set up).
- Information about the synergies and relevant initiatives.
- News and announcements.
- Links to the project's social media channels and partner websites.
- The Network of Interest (NoI).
- Access to public deliverables, newsletters, press releases, the [INSPIRE Zenodo community](#) and public materials.
- The INSPIRE Policy Dashboard and its components (It now includes the Rural typology on social exclusion and the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment. Later on it will also include the Policy recommendations).
- A dedicated page for the Advisory Board (AB). The AB currently includes 7 experts, representatives of marginalised groups, local authorities, academia, social economy, EU

stakeholders and civil society. Their guidance supports the project activities, ensuring alignment with real-world social inclusion needs.

Finally, during the lifespan of the project, the website will also host the websites of the Smart Village labs, the MOOCs of the training programme and the follower cases.

The site also features a newsletter subscription button (redirecting them to the LinkedIn Newsletter), allowing users and stakeholders to stay up to date with the latest project developments. For any inquiries, visitors can reach out via the dedicated contact form: <https://inspireprojecteu.eu/contact-us/>

Content development is a collaborative effort, with all project partners expected to contribute by providing news, updates, and relevant material. A report form is available to the consortium for this reason, and can be found in Annex III. As the project evolves, the website is continuously updated with new publishable deliverables, promotional assets, and key developments. The News & Press Releases section, in particular, is refreshed regularly to reflect ongoing actions and achievements.

At the end of the project, the website should reach 6,000 unique visitors. To ensure the project stays on track, the website is monitored periodically to determine whether progress is sufficient or if additional efforts are needed. Site visits, user statistics, and other visitor metrics, such as pages per visit, time on site, and most viewed pages, are tracked using Google Analytics, to which the website has been registered since its launch.

From the launch of the website in M6 through the current period (March 2025 - March 2026), the **website** has attracted **5,789 users** (updated on 27/03/2026).

Looking ahead, the INSPIRE website will continue to evolve as a dynamic communication tool, with regular updates on project results and new collaborations. The news and events page will be expanded to highlight partner activities and external synergies. Continuous monitoring of analytics will guide improvements, ensuring the website meets its goal of exceeding 6,000 unique visitors by project completion.

4.2.2 Social Media Accounts

The project’s social media accounts (SMAs) are among the main pillars of promoting the project’s news, events, and activities. INSPIRE utilises social media accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, Bluesky (M4), X and YouTube (M12). The above-mentioned accounts, except YouTube and Bluesky, have been launched in M3 (December 2024). If any needs arise, other social media may be used in the future. Table 6 contains URL links to INSPIRE’s existing social media accounts.

Table 6. INSPIRE’s SMAs

Social media platform	Account name	URL
LinkedIn	INSPIRE project EU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/inspire-project-eu/
Facebook	Inspire project EU	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61569429994625
Bluesky	INSPIRE project	https://bsky.app/profile/inspireprojecteu.bsky.social

Social media platform	Account name	URL
X		https://x.com/INSPIRE_EU1
YouTube		https://www.youtube.com/@INSPIREproject-eu

The project’s social media will be continuously updated in English with news about the project’s activities and results, pilot warm-up events, project events and workshops, scientific news, and updates from organisations/associations that promote social inclusion and innovation in rural areas, as well as news from related EU projects, etc. The frequency of social media posts depends on the availability of news about the activities and results of the project.

In addition, hashtags are used on the project’s posts to help stakeholders easily find them and encourage interaction. The hashtags used on the project’s social media accounts are:

- **#inspireproject**
- **#horizoneurope**
- **#socialinclusion**
- **#socialexclusion**
- **#innovation**
- **#socialentrepreneurship**
- **#ruralareas**
- **#smartvillagelabs**
- **#sustainability**
- **#wellbeing**
- **#empowerment**
- **#capacitybuilding**
- **#periurbanareas**
- **#coastalareas**
- **#mountainousareas**
- **#democraticengagement**
- **#civicparticipation**
- **#ruraldevelopment**
- **#vulnerablegroups**
- **#socialservices**
- **#socialeconomy**
- **#governanceframeworks**
- **#smartvillage**
- **#digitalinclusion**

Q-PLAN is responsible for the administration of INSPIRE’s social media accounts. All partners are encouraged to follow these accounts, engage with the content, and disseminate the project-related updates through their own organisational channels to help broaden outreach and visibility. As seen in Figure 16, which captures examples of such engagement, some partners have shown strong and consistent support by resharing posts, engaging through comments, and publishing their own content referencing the project. To maximise the impact of INSPIRES’s dissemination and communication efforts, continued and collective involvement from all partners remains essential.

Figure 16: Partners’ SMAs

4.2.2.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn constitutes a significant networking tool for professionals, offers a more institutional approach and has therefore been selected as a core social media channel. The project’s [LinkedIn page](#) was set up in M3 (December 2024), and it focuses on presenting the project, its objectives and results. All partners are responsible for timely updating and sharing their inputs to ensure their activities are duly promoted.

Figure 17: LinkedIn account

As shown in Figure 17, the LinkedIn page currently has 635 followers (updated on 27/03/2026).

According to Figure 18, the followers come from various industries, with the majority representing higher education, Civic and Social Organisations, Research services, Non-profit organisations, and related sectors. These backgrounds closely align with those of the project's partners and the key stakeholders the project aims to engage.

Figure 18: LinkedIn's followers' demographics

Given that the primary target audience on LinkedIn is the academic and research community, the project will continue to follow and further finetune its D&C strategy to focus on evidence-based content, thought leadership, and the sharing of expert knowledge. It will keep sharing project updates and findings, academic insights, and event-related content in a compelling and accessible way.

In addition, the project will continue making use of news items, articles, and press releases to boost media attention and spark online discussions. LinkedIn’s networking features will also be actively used to connect with research communities, foster dialogue through comment threads and groups, and highlight contributions from academic collaborators. Through this approach, the project aims to further build visibility, foster trust, and strengthen engagement within the scholarly ecosystem.

4.2.2.3 Facebook

A Facebook account was created in M3 (December 2024) with the aim of building a strong community in various ways, such as posting useful, relevant and interesting links. Facebook provides a fast, free connection to a significant number of stakeholders, so it gives the INSPIRE project an opportunity to share news and results. Like all INSPIRE social media accounts, the project’s Facebook page is regularly updated either with posts related to the project or other related projects and initiatives. In M18 the project’s Facebook page has 692 followers (updated on 27/03/2026).

Figure 19: Facebook account

4.2.2.2 Bluesky

A Bluesky account was launched in M4 (January 2025) to strengthen engagement with stakeholders and other European projects through the sharing of short updates for important steps of the project. This microblogging format facilitates the clear and rapid communication of INSPIRE’s objectives and activities. As shown in Figure 20, the Bluesky page currently has 28 followers (updated on 27/03/2026).

Figure 20: Bluesky Account

4.2.2.2 X

An X account was launched in M3 (December 2024), aiming to build engagement with stakeholders and other European projects through the exchange of quick, frequent messages. X is known for communicating via short messages. That helps project stakeholders understand, quickly and easily, what INSPIRE is and what it does. Figure 21 shows that the X page currently has 28 followers (updated on 27/03/2026).

Figure 21: X Account

4.2.2.4 YouTube

Finally, the INSPIRE YouTube channel was established in M12, coinciding with the completion of the animated communication video outlined in section 4.1.4 (Promotional video). This channel is chosen to consolidate project videos in a singular, easily accessible location. The primary objective behind creating the YouTube channel is to disseminate promotional videos, leveraging the platform to expose the project to a broader audience. To date, the channel has 28 subscribers and the informational video of INSPIRE has received 531 views. The video was also shared on all other social media, collectively receiving 1,819 views (updated on 27/03/2026).

Figure 22: YouTube Account

Moving forward, INSPIRE’s social media strategy will focus on ensuring consistent and engaging updates across LinkedIn, Facebook, Bluesky, X, and YouTube, highlighting project milestones, events, and scientific results. Greater emphasis will be placed on multimedia content such as pilot updates, short videos, and infographics to broaden outreach. The use of project hashtags will continue to enhance visibility, while tagging partners and relevant stakeholders will strengthen engagement. All partners will be encouraged to actively share, comment, and cross-promote content to expand the project’s reach and impact.

4.2.3 Online newsletter and mailing list

The project has committed to producing a total of six (6) bi-annual newsletters. The project uses [LinkedIn as the distribution platform](#). Each issue highlights key activities and developments from the preceding six months and is aimed at keeping stakeholders, followers, and interested parties well-informed about the project’s progress.

The newsletters are shared with a targeted audience, including all individuals who have subscribed through the project’s LinkedIn. In addition to email distribution, each issue is also made publicly available in the [“Newsletters” section of the project website](#).

Each issue is prepared by Q-PLAN with content contributions from all consortium partners when relevant. While the final content is agreed upon collaboratively, each issue-typically structured as shown in Figure 23, includes the following key sections:

- Overview: A brief summary of the issue.
- News from our Pilot Cases: Highlights from the activities and events performed by our Smart Village Labs.
- Project Activities: Major activities completed during the past six months.
- Communication activities: Coverage of the project’s involvement in relevant events and updated on collaborative efforts with our synergies.
- Future developments: Plans for the coming period and upcoming activities.

Figure 23: Latest newsletter issue

Anyone interested can subscribe or unsubscribe at any time through the newsletter section in the project’s LinkedIn account, fully in line with GDPR regulations. Although the standard frequency for publication is one issue every six months, additional ad-hoc editions may be released when significant updates or urgent information needs to be shared. At this stage, two (2) online newsletters were prepared and distributed through LinkedIn on M7 (April 2025) and M13 (October 2025). All partners are expected to support dissemination by sharing each newsletter through their own communication channels, thereby maximising reach and visibility.

Looking ahead, the project will continue releasing bi-annual newsletters until all six planned issues are completed, with the upcoming editions scheduled for M19, M24, M30, and M36. Each newsletter will maintain the established structure, providing stakeholders with clear updates on progress, collaborations, events, and upcoming activities. Q-PLAN will manage content and distribution with contributions from partners, while also implementing targeted promotion strategies to increase the number of subscribers through the website, social media, and partner channels. Ad-hoc editions will additionally be issued to share urgent or noteworthy developments.

4.2.4 Scientific publications

During the project, at least five (5) scientific publications will be published in scientific journals. Publications in impactful peer-reviewed scientific journals is one of our key channels for dissemination. INSPIRE will disseminate the research and experimental results via scientific articles and conference presentations. The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. Some publications are currently under preparation, and after being published, they will be reported in D6.4 - Dissemination and communication results.

An indicative list of journals that can be used under the context of the project is given in the following table:

Table 7. Indicative Journals for dissemination of INSPIRE’s results

Title	Impact factor	Title	Impact factor
Social Issues and Policy Review	9.857	Journal of Environmental Innovation and Societal Transition	5.7
Journal of Rural Studies	5.157	Review of Public Administration and Management	9.390
Regional Studies	4.672	Journal of Economic Perspectives	5.012
Sociologia Ruralis	3.2		

In addition, all authors are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publications of project news and results. Each partner will make an effort to produce publications in the highest quality, which not only reflects on the consortium’s reputation but also on the INSPIRE project. All publications must cite or/and refer to the EU contribution and project grant agreement number, as required in Article 17 of Grant Agreement No. 101136592.

4.2.5 Press releases and other publications

Press releases play a vital role in the project’s dissemination and communication strategy. Issued on an ad-hoc basis, they serve as a tool to highlight key achievements, progress milestones, and upcoming events, ensuring that stakeholders remain informed and engaged. These releases not only communicate essential updates but also help to attract interest and reinforce the visibility of the project at both local and European levels.

Press releases also help tell the story of the project through short articles that highlight success stories and real results. When needed, general press releases are prepared to reach stakeholders at the EU level and support wider visibility.

At this stage of the project, three (4) press releases have been produced and published on the INSPIRE website, along with multiple News Items (as seen in the dedicated section [News & Press Releases](#)). Two of them were issued following the project meetings and one following the creation of the project’s informational video:

- **Press Release 1:** Announced the INSPIRE kick-off meeting hosted at Mundo Matongé in Brussels, Belgium by WR on October 9th, 2024 (M3, December 2024).
- **Press Release 2:** Announced the INSPIRE second project meeting held in Lublin, Poland by ERDN on the 9th and 10th of April, 2025 (M7, April 2025)
- **Press Release 3:** Announced the INSPIRE project informational video (M12, September 2025)
- **Press Release 4:** Announced the INSPIRE third project meeting held in Dublin, Ireland, by The Wheel on the 8th and 9th of October, 2025 (M13, October 2025)

Figure 24: 2nd Press Release

All press releases have been circulated among consortium partners to support wide dissemination efforts. They have also been promoted across project communication channels.

Moreover, many INSPIRE partners have published project results in scientific conferences (as also highlighted in Section 4.3.2). A list of the project’s conference publications is provided in the following table:

No	Title	Year	Conference
1	A Territorial Topology of Social Exclusion in European Rural Areas (RUG)	2025	RSAI-BIS Congress in Cork
2	A New Typology of European Rural Regions Based on Social Exclusion (UB)	2025	XLIX International Conference on Regional Science in Pamplona
3	Network of Interest (NoI): A Tool for Social Inclusion in Rural Areas (ERDN)	2025	XXI Conference European Rural Development Network “Food System Transition for Sustainable Rural Development”, in Bucharest Romania
4	Smart Village Labs for Social Inclusion: Enhancing Rural Governance through the INSPIRE Project (ERDN)	2025	

Finally, a blog entry on the flagship report on rural social exclusion drivers was prepared and published in the [blog of the “Asociación Española de Ciencia Regional”](#) (García, M.; López-Tamayo, J.; Moreno, R.; Royuela, V. “¿Está Europa escuchando a sus zonas rurales más vulnerables?” La Riqueza de las Regiones).

4.3 INSPIRE events

4.3.1 Project events and workshops

Events serve as powerful communication tools, helping to share the project's goals, vision, and outcomes with a wider audience. Over the course of the project, a series of events, from warm-up events in the pilots to capacity building for groups in a vulnerable situation, underscore the project's dedication to social inclusion in the pilot areas and have been and will continue to be organised to exchange knowledge and build capacity, disseminate results to the multi-actor policy network of interest, and present final achievements to stakeholders (Final Conference).

The project's events and workshops are covered through the project's social media channels and news items published on the website. In addition, the Dissemination and Communication Manager provides support and guidance to partners when needed, to help promote their activities effectively.

The project events and engagement activities are presented in the following list:

- **Smart Village Labs' workshops:** Focusing on the inclusion of the local community and groups in a vulnerable situation, the Smart Village Labs deploy co-creation workshops, warm-up events, capacity-building workshops, user-innovation consultation workshops and local sustainability workshops. Up until now, **all pilots have already deployed two warm-up events each**, as part of Task 3.2, aiming to raise awareness of the local audiences and communicate the project. The pilots have also already deployed **seven co-creation workshops** to establish the Smart Village Labs. More information is included in D3.2 Smart Village labs governance frameworks and operating models.
- **Networking events and validation workshops:** Focusing on disseminating the project's results to interested stakeholders, as well as on validating the results, the project will deploy multiple networking and validation events. These events include the validation workshop, the EU-wide networking event, the pan-European virtual workshop with the NoI, and the project's Final Conference, where the final achievements of the project will be unveiled (M36), providing a comprehensive overview of the project's outcomes and advancements.
- **Interviews and surveys:** The project has already employed multiple engagement activities such as a virtual validation workshop, a Delphi survey, interviews with QH stakeholders, national surveys in the focus countries, CATI surveys, paper-based interviews in the pilot areas, and interviews with policy stakeholders in the pilots and focus groups in the pilots. It will continue to employ such activities to make sure that the opinions of key stakeholders are taken into account in its research.

4.3.2 External events

The project partners have participated in 12 events, including conferences, congresses, forums and seminars. These participations have enabled partners to maintain close contact with key audiences, exchange knowledge, and effectively communicate the project’s value propositions and results.

The selected events, both scientific and business-oriented, were aligned with the project’s knowledge domains, target sectors, and stakeholder interests. Through participation, partners stayed up to date with the latest developments in research and industry across Europe, contributed to the exchange of knowledge within relevant communities, and fostered meaningful interactions with key stakeholders, while simultaneously disseminating project outcomes.

During these events, partners should follow the below dissemination and communication guidelines:

- When presenting, the general project presentation should be used with any modifications necessary to this file, keeping the same template unless the event considers it mandatory to use the event’s template;
- During the event, it is important to disseminate the project’s promotional material (leaflets, posters, etc.);
- A series of photos to be taken to document the events;
- Each partner is requested to inform the Dissemination and Communication Manager of their participation and submit photos within ten days after the event;
- All partners are requested to complete the relevant section in the "Dissemination and Communication reporting" file (Annex IV & V) within three weeks of each event.

The following table provides an overview of the external events attended by the partners.

Table 8: External events

No	Type of activity	Date	Description
1	Event	28 April 2025	SEERC participated in the ACCTING Final Conference “Empowering Change: Building a Fair and Inclusive Green Deal” in Brussels, presenting the INSPIRE project during a dedicated session featuring projects working with populations in vulnerable situations, focusing on inclusion, sustainability, and grassroots innovation.
2	Event	14-15 May 2025	MedINA presented INSPIRE in the FUTURAL "EU-wide Rural Innovation Forum (EU-RIF)" in Zelaieta Zentroa (Amorebieta-Etxano, Spain).
3	Event	15-16 May 2025	Display of information on INSPIRE in EASPD’s project desk (leaflet and project slides) at EASPD’s international conference in Gandia, Spain through leaflet.
4	Event	28 May 2025	Sharing of the INSPIRE info sheet at The Wheel national conference
5	Conference	19 June 2025	RUG participated in the RSAI-BIS Congress in Cork, presenting some of the drivers of social exclusion in rural versus urban areas.

No	Type of activity	Date	Description
6	Event	June 2025	ESN participated in the European Social Services Conference (ESSC) in Aarhus, Denmark, presenting the project in the Walking Practice Fair, reaching around 700 participants, including local, regional and national authorities, international organisations, CSOs and innovators.
7	Event	2 September 2025	MedINA presented the project at the "Smart Villages" conference organised by the Attica Islands Regional Unit on the island of Salamina.
8	Event	23 September 2025	The Wheel participated with a stand at a local Community Associations Seminar in Cork.
9	Conference	22 September 2025	ERDN presented INSPIRE at the 21st ERDN Conference in Bucharest
10	Event	October 2025	Display of information on INSPIRE in EASPD's project desk (leaflet and project slides) at EASPD's international conference in Turin, Italy, through leaflet
11	Conference	16 October 2025	UB presented the typology of social exclusion across European rural regions at the XLIX International Conference on Regional Science in Pamplona
12	Event	20 November 2025	SEE presented INSPIRE at the ESIRA and SERIGO workshop "Harnessing social inclusion for rural resilience in Europe"

4.3.3 Final conference

By the end of the project, a closing event (EU-wide Final Conference in M36) will take place, organised under the lead of Q-PLAN. The aim of this conference is to attract interested stakeholders from the project's target groups, to spread the word for INSPIRE's accumulated knowledge and to present the project's final results and achievements as well as to promote their uptake across Europe. INSPIRE partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their own networks. Conversations about the organisation of the Final Conference will begin early on, during the 4th Project Meeting.

4.4 Synergies with relevant projects/initiatives

Synergies aim to promote collaboration and knowledge exchange while also achieving more efficient and effective use of their resources. These include Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects (i.e., ESIRA, SERIGO, etc.), as well as initiatives and networks linked to our partners.

Synergies include (without being limited to) the following actions:

- including the sister project's logo and its website on the INSPIRE website;
- participation in events organised by similar projects;
- dissemination of INSPIRE promotional material in similar projects' events;

- invitations to participate in INSPIRE’s events;
- exchange of news and dissemination through other projects’ channels.

A Synergies list was created to depict the established synergies and the projects approached, and is available on the project’s drive. Project partners are expected to identify similar projects and initiatives that might be interested in collaboration and should regularly enrich the list. All partners should keep in mind that the INSPIRE dissemination and communication strategy cannot reach its full potential unless meaningful collaboration with related projects is established.

From the start of the project, INSPIRE has established strong, meaningful synergies with the other two (2) sister projects under the same topic, namely “ESIRA” and “SERIGO”. These synergies focus not only on maximising dissemination and communication outreach, but also on coordinating research activities. Beyond these, INSPIRE has also established and now leverages **synergies with 7 relevant initiatives**, as shown in the following table:

Table 9: INSPIRE’s sister projects/relevant initiatives

No	Project name	Type of project/initiative	Description
1	ESIRA	Horizon Europe	ESIRA focuses on strengthening social innovation ecosystems in rural areas. The project promotes collaboration between social economy actors, local communities and policymakers in order to address social challenges and support inclusive rural development.
2	SERIGO	Horizon Europe	SERIGO aims to enhance social inclusion, resilience and wellbeing in rural areas through community-based research and social innovation. The project works with pilot regions to co-develop solutions addressing social inequalities and rural development challenges.
3	R-Map	Horizon Europe	R-Map investigates the impact of remote working on urban–rural relations in Europe. The project maps and analyses how remote work influences migration patterns, territorial inequalities and development opportunities in rural and urban areas.
4	SMART ERA	Horizon Europe	SMART ERA supports the development of smart and resilient rural communities by promoting innovation-driven solutions. The project develops integrated “innovation packages” combining governance, technology and entrepreneurship to tackle rural depopulation and socio-economic challenges.
5	SPACE-NEST	SMP-COSME	SPACE-NEST aims to revitalise underused rural spaces by transforming them into hubs for sustainable and socially driven economic activities. The project promotes community-led regeneration aligned with the principles of the New European Bauhaus.
6	CREASSE	Erasmus+	CREASSE supports the development of social and solidarity economy initiatives in rural areas. The project focuses on strengthening inclusion and participation of vulnerable groups through collaborative social enterprise models and community-based initiatives.

7 BIOFAIRNET Horizon Europe

BIOFAIRNET develops a digital network supporting fair and sustainable bio-circular economy value chains. The project connects stakeholders across sectors such as agriculture and mining to co-create solutions for more equitable and sustainable resource use.

The INSPIRE project has actively engaged with the above relevant initiatives to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange. All synergies have been formally announced through the project's website and social media channels. Representatives of ESIRA and SERIGO were invited to join the INSPIRE Network of Interest (NoI) and to participate in the ERDN conference in Bucharest. In addition, INSPIRE partners were invited to take part in activities organised by SERIGO, including its Community of Practice workshop, and a joint exchange session between ESIRA and SERIGO was planned to facilitate further dialogue. These activities demonstrate INSPIRE's commitment to maintaining continuous interaction with thematically aligned initiatives and strengthening cross-project knowledge exchange.

Moreover, during the 2nd project meeting of INSPIRE (Lublin, April 2025), representatives of the sister projects SERIGO and ESIRA participated in the event as invited speakers. During the meeting, the projects presented their ongoing activities and research focus, providing an opportunity to exchange experiences related to rural social innovation, social economy and inclusion in rural areas. The discussions contributed to identifying potential areas of cooperation and strengthening the dialogue between the participating projects, while also helping to connect INSPIRE's work with broader European initiatives addressing similar challenges.

A highlight of the collaboration actions undertaken by INSPIRE is the Clustering event on September 26, 2025, which took place as part of the 21st ERDN Conference in Bucharest. A dedicated session brought together representatives of several related initiatives, including SERIGO, ESIRA and SPACE-NEST, and provided a platform for exchanging knowledge and exploring opportunities for collaboration among projects working on rural social inclusion and social innovation. During the session, participants presented their activities, discussed methodological approaches and explored possibilities for future cooperation, including knowledge exchange, policy learning and participation in joint initiatives.

As presented in deliverable D6.3 "INSPIRE website", the project's website features a subpage titled "Synergies". This subpage comprises a list of initiatives and sister projects with which INSPIRE has established collaborations, presented in blocks with logos, along with a short description and the links to their individual websites.

Figure 25: INSPIRE's Synergies

The INSPIRE project aims to keep establishing synergies with key projects and initiatives, including projects funded under the topics HORIZON-CL2-2022-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-02 and HORIZON-CL2-2021-TRANSFORMATIONS-01-03, other active relevant Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, and projects funded under other EU programmes.

Results from clustering activities will be reported in **D6.4 Dissemination and communication results** (M36).

4.5 Network of Interest - NoI

As part of T5.1, ERDN is in charge of bringing together key stakeholders from several rural areas in Europe to set up an interactive multi-actor Network of Interest (NoI), which includes (i) policy makers, (ii) NGOs and vulnerable groups organisations, and (iii) social enterprises. The NoI supports social empowerment of groups in a vulnerable situation through the social economy, supporting at the same time the outreach of the INSPIRE project and the dissemination of its results. In order to reach a wider pool of stakeholders, partners leverage their extensive network as indicated below:

Table 10. Consortium networks

Consortium networks for dissemination and exploitation results	
European Rural Development Network (ERDN)	Global Social Economy Forum (GSEF)
European Social Network (ESN)	European Smart Villages Forum (ESVF)
European Association of Service providers with Persons with Disabilities (EASPD)	Global Network for Entrepreneurs with Disabilities (GNED)

The multi-actor network will not only facilitate the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and experiences, but also promote collective action that enhances social inclusion, equality, and sustainable economic development in rural areas. By uniting these diverse actors, the NoI contributes to the strengthening of social cohesion within rural communities and to improving the resilience and adaptability of vulnerable groups in the face of socio-economic challenges.

The NoI is structured to ensure that all relevant stakeholders, including marginalised communities and at-risk populations, have an active voice in shaping the development of social economy initiatives. In addition, to fostering direct collaboration, the NoI plays an important role in the outreach and dissemination of the INSPIRE project’s results. By connecting with a broad spectrum of local, regional, and national stakeholders, the NoI serves as a conduit for disseminating project findings, raising awareness, and advocating for policy change that benefits vulnerable groups and strengthens the role of the social economy.

Additionally, to maximise the impact of this network, partners leverage their extensive existing networks, drawing on relationships with local government authorities, community leaders, and sector-specific organisations across rural Europe. This ensures that the NoI reaches a broad and diverse audience and facilitates cross-border learning and collaboration.

Furthermore, the project will ensure continuous engagement through digital platforms, enabling real-time collaboration and exchange of resources, while also incorporating feedback mechanisms that allow for adaptive learning throughout the project cycle. These activities will not only raise awareness of the INSPIRE project’s outcomes but will also help integrate innovative ideas and evidence-based practices into the wider policy and social economy landscapes.

Through this approach, the **Network of Interest** will become a cornerstone of both the **INSPIRE project** and ongoing efforts to build resilient, inclusive, and sustainable rural communities across Europe.

The following actions have been taken up until M18 towards the creation and development of the NoI:

1. Establishing an operational framework and methodology

The foundation for the activities was the implementation of the Quadruple Helix model. A decision was made to base the network on the cooperation of four pillars: public administration, civil society organisations, the private sector (social enterprises), and the scientific community.

- Defining the form of cooperation: An informal and flexible model was adopted, based on voluntary participation, no membership fees, and mutual trust.
- The Task 5.1 leader, ERDN, was responsible for identifying members, logistics for meetings, and moderating discussions.

2. Membership base development (Recruitment)

Recruitment activities brought measurable results in the form of **41 active members**. The process followed is depicted below:

- Creation of a simplified data framework: A data management process limited to a minimum (name/organization, e-mail) was developed, which lowered the barrier to entry into the network.
- Diversification of participant profiles: Targeted invitations resulted in broad representation:
- The largest groups are **civil society organisations** (37.14%) and **academia** (31.43%). **Social enterprises** also have a significant share (20%).
- Geographical expansion: Recruitment covered **entities from 16 countries**, with the strongest representation from Poland (12 members) and a significant share from Greece, Italy, Ireland, Belgium and Türkiye. Other members come from countries including Latvia, Slovakia, Norway, Spain, and France.

3. Dissemination and promotional activities

In order to increase the visibility of Nol and attract new members, the following steps were taken:

- Promotion of participation: Digital channels (online forms) and direct email contacts (by ERDN) were used to invite key stakeholders. The identification of potential Nol members was also supported by other project partners.
- Networking event: Recruitment and promotion also took place during the 21st ERDN Conference in Bucharest.

4. Ongoing coordination and planning

- Ongoing promotion: Using project events and meetings to establish direct relationships with potential members.
- Communication channels: Using direct mailing and digital tools to streamline the onboarding process for new members.
- The list of Nol members (a dedicated excel file shared in the project's drive) is monitored on an ongoing basis, which allows for ongoing analysis of the structure and reach of the network.

Results from the activities regarding the Nol will be reported in **D5.1 INSPIRE policy recommendations** (M32).

4.6 Practice Abstracts

INSPIRE is being and will be elaborating two deliverables that contain the project's Practice Abstracts (PAs) in the framework of enhancing the dissemination and policy uptake of the INSPIRE key results. The PAs are produced under T6.1 to facilitate the flow of information from INSPIRE to end-users and share relevant, innovative and practice-oriented knowledge. The PAs will be prepared by UB, ESN, WR, SEERC, PEDAL and WHEEL, each partner responsible for their respective asset, using guidance and templates elaborated by ERDN based on the EIP-AGRI common format (with the assistance of all partners, especially SEERC). More specifically, as also seen in Table 11:

- Deliverable **D6.7 – Practice Abstracts – batch 1** contains 2 practice abstracts: (i) Territorial typology of EU rural areas (prepared by UB) and (ii) the Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment (prepared by ESN). The deliverable is being prepared and to be submitted at the end of M18.
- Deliverable **D6.8 – Practice Abstracts – batch 2** will contain 4 practice abstracts: (i) Smart Village labs (prepared by WR); (ii) the Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard (prepared by SEERC); (iii) the Social economy solutions deployment roadmaps (prepared by PEDAL); and the (iv) Portfolio of INSPIRE innovative solutions (prepared by WHEEL).

Table 11: INSPIRE's Practice Abstracts

#	Lead partner	PAs included	Responsible partner	Deliverable	Time
Practice Abstracts – batch 1	ERDN	Territorial typology of EU rural areas	UB	D6.7	M18
		Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment	ESN		
Practice Abstracts – batch 2	ERDN	Smart Village labs	WR	D6.8	M36
		Rural Social Inclusion Policy Dashboard	SEERC		
		Social economy solutions deployment roadmaps	PEDAL		
		Portfolio of INSPIRE innovative solutions	WHEEL		

In early 2026, the preparation of Practice Abstracts (PA) Batch 1 was initiated under Task 6.1. ERDN prepared and circulated the Practice Abstract template and guidelines based on the EIP-AGRI format, providing partners with instructions regarding the required structure and the practice-oriented character of the abstracts. UB prepared the Practice Abstract describing the “Territorial typology of EU rural areas” and submitted the completed version using the EU CAP Network template. In parallel, ESN prepared a draft Practice Abstract presenting the “Services and Social Economy Atlas on Rural Empowerment”, based on the results of the Atlas developed within WP2. The submitted document was subsequently reviewed by ERDN, which introduced editorial refinements aimed at simplifying the language and strengthening the practical orientation of the description in line with the Practice Abstract format used by the European Commission. As a result, both Practice Abstracts reached an advanced stage of preparation and were aligned with the EU CAP Network Practice Abstract requirements and the dissemination objectives of the INSPIRE project.

4.7 Dissemination channels

A tentative list of EU dissemination channels that may be utilised by INSPIRE throughout its duration is provided below:

- **CORDIS** is the EC primary source of results from projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for R&I.
- The **Horizon Results Booster** addresses projects eager to go beyond their dissemination and exploitation obligations under Horizon funding schemes.
- **Horizon Results** is a repository of Key Exploitable Results of EU-funded research and innovation projects.
- **Open Research Europe** is an open-access publishing platform that beneficiaries can use to publish any research results coming from R&I funded programmes, and it is in line with the EU's open science policy.
- **Horizon Dashboard** is an interactive knowledge platform where statistics and data on EU Research and Innovation programmes can be extracted.
- **Eurofound**. The European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions is a European Union Agency, whose role is to assist in the development of better social, employment and work-related policies.
- **The Horizon Magazine** is a publication by the European Commission that highlights cutting-edge European research and innovation, showcasing how EU-funded projects tackle global challenges and advance scientific progress.
- **EU-FarmBook** is a Horizon Europe project working at regional, national, and European level, to build an Online Platform, that offers a collection of vetted best practices for farmers and foresters, offered by Horizon research projects.
- **EU Info-days, workshops and conferences**
- **Zenodo** is a widely used open-access research repository to ensure the long-term availability and accessibility of INSPIRE's results. A dedicated [INSPIRE Zenodo community](#) has already been created and is constantly fed with project results.

5. Timeline and implementation plan

In Figure 26, an updated action plan of INSPIRE’s dissemination and communication activities is presented, spanning the whole duration of the project.

Activity	Responsible Partner	Related WP	2024												2025												2026												2027											
			1st year												2nd year												3rd year																							
			M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36												
Development of promotional material																																																		
Logo	Q-PLAN	WP6	■	■																																														
Templates (report, presentation and letterhead)		All WPs			■	■																																												
Leaflet, poster, and infographic		WP6			■	■																																												
Promotional video		WP6											■	■																																				
Website																																																		
Development and operation of project’s website	Q-PLAN	WP6	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■																																						
Publicity through project’s website	All partners	All WPs											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■										
Publicity through partners’ website	All partners	All WPs											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■										
Social media networks																																																		
Creation of social media accounts (LinkedIn, Facebook, Bluesky, X, Youtube)	Q-PLAN	WP6	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■																																						
Publicity through projects’ social media	All partners	All WPs											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■										
Publicity through partners’ social media	All partners	All WPs											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■									
Publicity through project YouTube channel	Q-PLAN	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■									
Digital presence																																																		
Recipients list (within LinkedIn)	Q-PLAN	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■										
E-newsletter	Q-PLAN	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■									
Publications																																																		
Non – scientific (press releases)	All partners	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■									
Scientific publications and conference papers	All partners	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■								
External events																																																		
Exhibitions, business events, information days etc.	All partners	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■									
Scientific events, conferences etc.	All partners	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■								
Project workshops																																																		
Trainings, workshops and webinars	All partners	All WPs											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■								
Final Conference																																																		
EU-wide Final Conference	Q-PLAN	All WPs																																																
Synergies with related projects/initiatives																																																		
Synergies with related projects/initiatives	ERDN, all partners	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■									
Network of Interest (NoI)																																																		
Network of Interest (NoI)	ERDN, all partners	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■									
EU dissemination channels																																																		
CORDIS , Horizon Results Booster , Horizon Results, Open Research Europe , Horizon Dashboard , Eurofound,Horizon Magazine, EU-FarmBook EU Info-days, workshops and conferences	Q-PLAN	WP6											■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■								

Figure 26: INSPIRE’s timeline

6. Key Performance Indicators and monitoring

To assess the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication strategy, a set of KPIs is used. All dissemination activities are systematically tracked, with their results compared against these KPIs to determine whether the project is on the right path or if additional efforts are needed to meet its communication goals.

According to the table below, many KPIs have already been achieved and are close to the target. The project will continue to follow the Dissemination and Communication strategy consistently for the best possible results.

Table 12: INSPIRE's dissemination KPIs (updated on 27/03/2026)

Indicator	Target (impact)	Current Status (M18)	Comments
Total visits to the project's website	≥ 6,000	5,789	-
Followers on social media accounts	≥ 500	1,411 LinkedIn 635, Facebook 692, Bluesky 28, X 28, YouTube 28	Achieved
Number of newsletters	6	2	-
Number of newsletter subscribers	≥ 200	293	Achieved
Number of publications in journals	≥ 5	-	-
Participation in external events	≥ 10	12	Achieved
Synergies with other initiatives	≥ 10	7	-
Network of Interest participants	≥ 60	41	-
Participants in Final Conference	≥ 75	-	-
Promotional video total views	≥ 500	1,819	Achieved
Participants in EU-wide networking event	≥ 40	-	-

To meet target values, project partners are expected to continuously carry out publicity actions and report all publicity and communication outcomes regularly. Q-PLAN is responsible for monitoring and supporting the INSPIRE dissemination activities.

Partners are required to provide detailed reports on all communication and dissemination actions through the INSPIRE "Dissemination and Communication Reporting Excel", which is sent to all partners via email. The table can be found in Annex VI. Q-PLAN notifies all partners in advance for input collection.

Any promotional material related to the project produced by a partner is reviewed by the WP6 leader, Q-PLAN. Each project partner should promptly contact Q-PLAN whenever they identify promotion opportunities, problems, or risks during the planning or implementation of publicity actions.

7. Conclusions

This final version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan builds upon the foundation established in D6.1 and reflects the progress achieved during the first period of the project (M18). While D6.1 focused primarily on laying the groundwork, such as the project's identity, social media presence, promotional material, D6.2 describes the objectives and the defined framework of the project's communication and dissemination strategy and provides an update of both the implemented and the foreseen communication and dissemination activities and corresponding channels.

The project consortium has so far managed to create a consistent and recognisable visual identity and branding for the INSPIRE project and has made considerable efforts to reach out to the targeted stakeholder groups and relevant networks. The project communication and dissemination activities are focused on raising awareness about the project's approach and development, through the established website, newsletters, press releases, an information video, project online media, activities, synergies, contributions with new knowledge and through participation in relevant events.

In terms of dissemination performance, the project has now met many of its KPIs and, in some cases, exceeded its early objectives. While the initial dissemination targets were set at 500 social media followers, the project now has more than 1,400 and has also exceeded the 200 target of newsletter subscribers. Moreover, partners have participated in 12 external events, and the informational video has been viewed by over 1800 viewers across the project's YouTube channel and other social media.

Another notable achievement is the consortium's active engagement with related initiatives. The project has established 7 synergies with other EU-funded projects and has already carried out many joint activities. These partnerships have broadened the project's network and amplified its visibility at the European level. Moreover, the Nol was established, currently bringing together 41 members from 16 countries. The Nol's dynamic development and the high participation of civil society organisations (over 37%) is a good step towards becoming a useful knowledge transfer platform.

Overall, while D6.1 established the structures and tools for dissemination, D6.2 shows how these have been translated into concrete actions and measurable impact. The consortium has met many of its original targets, expanded its communication strategy to include richer content and achieved significantly higher levels of stakeholder engagement than initially anticipated.

The project's future efforts will focus on deepening the connections made and networks built in local and EU context, to maximise the visibility and outreach of the INSPIRE project. To this end, all partners will keep on actively contributing to the communication and dissemination activities through the exploitation of the defined dissemination tools and channels, promoting and multiplying publicity of the project's aims and achievements and disseminating targeted messages to all relevant stakeholders.

As the project completes, results will be presented, and progress against targets will be reported in "D6.4 - Dissemination and communication results" (M36).

8. Annexes

8.1 Annex I – INSPIRE’s D&C Guidelines

8.2 Annex II – Templates

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

Text box to insert the event title

PRESENTER: Name Surname
LEAD BENEFICIARY: Company Name
DD/MM/YYYY | Venue

PARTNERS

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

Main Title Style

Main subtitle style

Main Title Style

Text template style

Text template style

2011/2024 Footer 4

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

VISIT: inspireprojecteu.eu
CONTACT: info@inspireprojecteu.eu

FOLLOW US:

INSPIRE project EU

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PARTNERS

inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

Dx.y Title

Beneficiary (Short Name)

DD/MM/YYYY

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inspire
SMART VILLAGE LABS

Contact details: konstas@qplan-intl.gr

Faded version of the Dx.y Title template slide content.

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8.3 Annex III – News reporting form

GA 101136592

1. News

Picture(s)	
Title	
News (main content)	<p>Please <u>insert here</u> the content in a <u>narrative way</u>, while trying to provide answers to the following questions (if applicable):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who was or will be the organisation(s) responsible for organising the activity or developing the solution / Who was or will it be for (target group or groups if applicable) • When did or will it take place or is / will be available (if applicable) • Where did or will it take place or is / will be available (if applicable) • Why is this activity important / Why did or will we need participation or contribution (if applicable) • How was or will it be implemented (very briefly) • What were or will be the main benefits or outcomes / results / conclusions
Key words/ hashtags (for social media)	

2. Attachments

Please attach any relevant pictures/ images as separate .png or .jpg files with as high resolution as possible.

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8.4 Annex IV – External attended events (dissemination and communication reporting sheet)

Events										
#	Event's Name	Thematic Focus	Date	Location	Registration fees	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission etc)	Deadline for abstract submission (if applicable)	Website	Added by (Partner)	Status
1										
2										
3										Cancelled Ongoing Done

8.5.2 Dissemination activities

Last Updated		DD/MM/YYYY								
#	Partner	Type of activity	Description/ title of activity	Date	Type of audience	Size of audience	Focus on vulnerable group (if applicable), and which	Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the activity	Comments
1										
2										
3		Conferences								
		Education and training events								
		Meetings								
		Clustering activities								
		Collaboration with EU-funded projects								
		Other scientific collaboration								
		Other scientific cooperation								
		Other								
					Research communities					
					Industry, business partners					
					Innovators					
					Investors					
					International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.)					
					EU Institutions					
					National authorities					
					Regional authorities					
					Local authorities					
					Civil society					
					Citizens					
					Specific end user communities					
									CANCELLED	
									DELIVERED	
									ONGOING	
									POSTPONED	

8.5.3 Publications

Last Updated		DD/MM/YYYY								
#	Type of PID	Type of publication	Title of the scientific publication	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	ISSN or eISSN	Publisher	Month of publication	Year of publication
1										
2	DOI									
3	Handle	select the list								
	ARK									
	URI									
	pURL									
	Other									
	None									
		Article in journal								
		Publication in conference proceeding/ workshop								
		Books/ monographs								
		Chapters in books								
		Thesis/ dissertation								
		Other								

Month of publication	Year of publication	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	Peer-reviewed	PID (Publisher version of record)	Book Title	Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	Type of publishing venue	Article processing costs that will be charged to the project
		Yes					Hybrid venue	
		No					Full open access venue	
							Full subscription venue	
			Yes					
			No					
								Yes
								No

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